

**POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS TO IMPROVE THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE
OF PUPILS FROM SINGLE-PARENT FAMILIES IN TORIT TOWN
EASTERN EQUATORIA STATE SOUTH SUDAN**

**Taban David Kamerino,¹ Dr. Elizabeth Ngozi Okpalaenwe,² Rev. Fr. Uchenna Kalu
Agwu³**

1. Psycho-Spiritual Institute Marist International University College

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ABSTRACT

Over the past several decades, the prevalence of single-parent families has continued to increase. Thus, this study focused on the relationship between single parenting and the academic performance of pupils in Primary schools in Torit Town, Eastern Equatoria South Sudan. The specific objectives were to assess the level of parental involvement in the academic performance of children in Torit Town South Sudan, to determine the influence of single parenting on the academic performance of primary school pupils, to examine the relationship between single parenting and academic performance of the primary school pupils, to identify the possible solutions to improve the academic performance of pupils from single parents in Torit Town. The study was anchored on attachment and psychological theories and quantitative approach with the correlational design was used. Questionnaires were used as an instrument for data collection. The simple random sampling technique was used to select the study participants. The study's target population is 80 pupils from single parents drawn from four primary schools. The data was analyzed using SPSS version 25.0 to produce descriptive statistics. Data was presented on tables and charts with frequency and percentages. From the findings, it was discovered that the majority of the single parents were female compared to their male counterparts, and the reason why they ended up as single parents was that most of the respondents answered that the parents separated. The study also found a weak positive relationship between single parenting and academic performance among pupils.

Key words: Single-parenting, Academic performance

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INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Single parenting affects children's performance in different ways. A single parent bringing children alone performed the duty of both the mother and the father, providing financial support in educating the children, necessities at home such as food, clothing and shelter and the overall well-being of the children.

Jarvis et al. (2023) study in the United Kingdom found out that despite the increase in frequency and normalization of non-traditional family structures in the UK, such as cohabitation, single parent, and stepparent families, we find that children in stable married families experience fewer externalizing behavior problems compared to children in other family structures.

Tobishima (2018) a study in Japan suggests that the low academic achievement of children in single-mother families may be caused by the mothers' low education levels and accompanying low income, whereas poor academic achievement of children in single-father families is likely to be mainly due to the absence of mothers rather than the fathers' low education levels. Based on the empirical evidence obtained in this paper, policy implications regarding the significance and limitations of economic support for single-parent families in terms of reducing educational inequality.

Mishra (2020) found that children of single parents in Germany increased their academic achievement when they received social support from family, friends, and teachers. Studies have suggested that such social support may be protective for these children, reducing the negative impact of single parenthood on their academic achievement. The availability of social support was positively associated with the overall well-being of single-parent families and subsequently with higher children's

academic achievement (van Bodengraven, 2021). This study explained the importance of comprehensively examining the context of single parenthood, encompassing aspects like social support, to fully comprehend its influence on the academic performance of children.

Over the past several decades, the incidence of single-parent families has continued to increase. According to Roger and Pryor (2007), single parents' level of education influences their children's socialization.

Children who grow up in single-parent or stepparent families are less successful as adults, particularly in the two domains of life, love, and work, which are most essential to happiness. Needless to say, not all children experience such negative effects. However, research shows that many children from disrupted families have a harder time achieving intimacy in a relationship, forming a stable marriage, or even holding a steady job (David, 2009).

According to Oyedele (1995), single parenting can be seen as a situation whereby only one of the parents raises the child or children. Single-parenthood can be defined as when one out of two people responsible for nurturing and child rearing is not available, and the work meant for two people is now carried out by only one person.

Ngusa and Gundula (2019) study in Kenya, found that kids from lower-income single-parent households had a high likelihood of performing poorly in school as compared to kids from single-parent households with higher income. Their findings further showed that children in low-income single-parent households have more challenges that hinder them from effective learning, for instance, a lack of books, low

motivation, and inappropriate attire for some school activities. The effect of income may be greater in the long run, as children in lower-income single-parent households may have more difficulty accessing appropriate education and resources, as they grow older.

Adewumi & Jethro (2012) in their study in Nigeria, concluded that when parents come to school regularly to know the well-being of their children, it reinforces the view in the child's mind that school and home are connected and that school is an integral part of the whole family's life. It can be said that the impact of parental involvement arises from parental values and educational aspirations and that these are exhibited continuously through parental enthusiasm and positive parenting style.

Abuya et al. (2019), in their study in Kenya, confirmed the trends and results in other studies, specifying that the educational level of single parents was crucial to their children's academic outcomes. Correspondingly, Thuba (2019) showed similar results, indicating that single parents' level of education considerably predicted their children's academic attainment, whereby children of educated single parents had a high likelihood of excelling in examinations and other school-related activities. For example, the effect of educational level may be mediated by a parent's ability to provide educational resources, a parent's expectations about their child's education, or a parent's ability to help their child at home.

Katamei and Omwono (2015), in their study in Kenya, concluded that when students perceive that their parents value education, they are more likely to feel competent and motivated in their studies. In fact, the academic encouragement parents provide is even more powerful than the support provided by friends and teachers. The

extent to which parents convey and communicate these expectations is more important. The more families discuss school issues, the more positive impact their expectations can have on their children's academic achievements.

Anyieth and Ayen's (2012) study in South Sudan found a moderately high positive link between students' home environments and dropout rates and a moderately high negative correlation between home environments and promotion rates. Based on the research findings, recommendations were made that parents should re-evaluate their parenting methods to influence the timing of marriage, enrolment, and, most importantly, the distribution of domestic workload on female learners in order to help reduce pressure on female learners in schools; parents should set high expectations and create conducive home environments for their children to improve their attitudes toward school.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Mullender-Wijnsma et al. (2014) studied improving academic performance of School-age children by physical activity in the classroom: 1-year program evaluation in Netherlands. A total of 228 children, the mean age was 8 years, with 122 boys and 106 girls from second or third grades of 6 elementary schools, were recruited from the northern Netherlands. A quasi-experimental design with a control group was used. Every school participated with a second and third-grade class. Three second-grade classes participated in the F&V intervention (N = 58). The other 3 second-grade classes formed the control group (N = 62). In the schools where grade 2 participated in the intervention, grade 3 formed the control group (N = 52) and in the schools where grade 2 formed the control group, grade 3 participated in the intervention (N = 56). This study shows that the intervention program can be implemented with success in elementary classrooms. The physically active academic lessons improved the academic achievement of third-grade children. Because of program evaluation outcomes, the intervention was improved, and in future studies, the effects of the improved intervention was investigated. The reviewed study did not take into consideration single parents. The literature gap was covered by the present study.

Taratori et al. (2012) studied identifying ways to improve schoolchildren's performance: the students' point of view in Greece. The data collected using content analysis as the research method uses free text as a research tool. The researcher used survey design to utilize the accumulated educational research aimed at exploring and bringing to the surface highly influential factors related to the social and academic goals. The research sample for this study was 3rd-year university students at the Department of Primary Education at the Democritus University of Thrace, and the

participant number was 170. Parents ought to be careful not to use expressions regarding their children that destroy their self-esteem. Low self-esteem lowers performance, and for this reason, students should be encouraged. In the reviewed study, the participants of choice were university students, while the current study concentrates on primary school children. The findings suggest that student achievement could be highly affected by a wide range of specific instructional strategies educators use in the everyday teaching and learning process. The study reviewed studied third year university student while the current study looked upon pupils from single parent. This is the gap to be filled by the current study.

Jepketer et al. (2015) conducted research on teachers' classroom strategy for enhancing students' performance in public secondary schools in Nandi County, Kenya. The study used descriptive survey design. The researcher used 30% as population sample size for the public secondary schools, 30% as population sample size for principals, 10% for teachers and 10% for the students. The target sample was (30) public secondary schools, (30) school principals, (85) teachers, (136) students and one County Director of Education. Stratified and simple random sampling techniques were used for the study. The findings of the study established that students continue to perform poorly in academics in some public secondary schools. It was further found out that strategies used by teachers to manage their classrooms including the teaching methods employed, managing student discipline and providing constant feedback through assessment influences students' performance to a greater extent. The study reviewed was more concentrated on the teacher aspect and left aside the student who does the actually learning. This is the gap to be filled by the current study.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The quantitative research approach was used in this study. Thus, the study employed the correlational design method. The use of this method was employed to allow the researcher to identify the relationship between variables. In this study, the target population of the pupils from the four mixed schools was 80. The primary pupils are from the upper classes, mostly above 18 years of age. However, the study targeted those from single parents. These participants are believed to have the information being sought by this study. The study draws its sample from a population of pupils in Torit Town, in the Eastern Part of South Sudan. Torit Town is the most significant Centre in Eastern Equatoria State because it is the capital of the state with proper settlement, and people come to trade in Torit Town.

A sample is made of smaller groups obtained from the accessible population while ensuring that the sample size is neither too large nor too small but relatively optimum, that is, one that fulfills the requirements of efficiency, representativeness, liability, and flexibility (Kothari, 2004). Slovin's Formula was used to arrive at the sample size, which has a confidence level of 95% and a margin error of 5%. The four Catholic primary schools were selected for the study as shown below.

Sample Matrix

Category	Target population	Sample size	Sampling techniques	%
St. Theresa Primary School	17	14	Purposive sampling	21
Torit East Primary School	22	18	Purposive sampling	28
Torit West Primary School	31	27	Purposive sampling	39
Our Lady of Holy Rosary Primary School	10	8	Purposive sampling	12
Total	80	67		

Table 1 shows that the study enlisted 67 respondents who were drawn from the four catholic primary schools. The purposive sampling method was used, meaning a sample from the target population was used to collect the data. This was because the number was manageable. A sample was drawn from the target population to enable the researcher to choose the representative group that can offer useful information for this study.

FINDINGS

Table 1: *The possible solutions to improve the academic performance*

Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Disagree	Disagree
My academic performance will improve if I get more support from the parent	12(20%)	24(40%)	6(10%)	4(6.7%)	14(23.3%)
Do teachers play their role as guardian to help provide the necessary moral, material and psychological support to students from single parents	6(10%)	34(56.7%)	6(10%)	7(11.7%)	7(11.7%)
My academic performance will improve if the school provided special attention and resources to students from single parents	4(6.7%)	27(45%)	9(15%)	6(10%)	14(23.3%)
Support from community well-wishers will greatly improve my academic performance	3(5%)	9(15%)	3(5%)	17(28.3%)	28(46.7%)
The government should prioritize the county bursary to cater for students from single-parent	16(26.7%)	26(43.3%)	1(1.7%)	7(11.7%)	10(16.7%)

The table above summarizes the findings regarding the possible solutions to improve the academic performance of students from single-parent families in Torit Town, South Sudan.

When asked whether their academic performance will improve if they get more support from their parents, 60% of the respondents were in agreement with the statement, 10% of the respondents were undecided and 30% of the respondents were in disagreement with the statement. We can therefore conclude that support from single parents will help improve the pupil's academic performance.

Participants were asked whether teachers play their role as guardians to help provide the necessary moral, material, and psychological support to students from single parents, 67% of the respondents were in agreement with the statement, 10% of the respondents were undecided and 23% of the respondents were in disagreement with the statement. We can therefore conclude that teacher play their role as guardians to help provide the necessary moral, material, and psychological support to students from single parents.

Respondents were asked whether their academic performance would improve if the school provided special attention and resources to students from single parents, 52% of the respondents were in agreement with the statement, 15% of the respondents were undecided and 33% of the respondents were in disagreement with the statement. We can therefore conclude that pupils from single-parents academic performance will improve if the school provides special attention and resources to them.

When asked whether support from community well-wishers will greatly improve their academic performance, 20% of the respondents were in agreement with the statement, 5% of the respondents were undecided and 75% of the respondents were in disagreement with the statement. We can therefore conclude that support from the

community well-wishers will not help improve pupils from single parents' academic performance.

Participants were asked whether the government should prioritize the county bursary to cater for students from single parents, 70% of the respondents were in agreement with the statement, 2% of the respondents were undecided and 28% of the respondents were in disagreement with the statement. We can therefore conclude that should government should prioritize the county bursary to cater to students from single parents. This result is supported by the findings of Taratori et al. (2012) which stressed that student achievement could be highly affected by a wide range of specific instructional strategies educators use in the everyday teaching and learning process.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes a significant relationship between single parents and academic performance. Specifically, single parents' inadequate supervision, poor parenting skills and inability to act as good role models could lead to pupil's poor performance in school. Most single-parent families are likely to face financial difficulties due to many financial obligations under the care of one parent.

The government has a great role to play in supporting pupils from single parents by setting aside bursary funds money and resources to help through financial difficulties. Single parents on the other hand should be supportive of their child because they carry a big responsibility to be both father and mother to the child in the absence of the other partner.

The study identified economic hardship, insufficient financial resources to support children's upbringing and education expenses therefore; they could not meet school requirements were identified as challenges facing pupils from single parent family. In addition, pupils from single parent had at the same time failed to get proper care from their parents, poor monitoring and/or supervision, poor emotional support and cognitive stimulation were also identified as challenges facing pupils from single parent household. For remedial measures, the study suggested guidance and counseling, identify and participating in income generating activities in order to maintain the family while supporting school activities that requires financial input of her/his children, provide guidance and counseling. Similarly, majority of low-income single parents should engage in small business to get money to support their pupils' education.

This suggests that parents' involvement through home works, creating conducive home environment for studying, motivating and setting realistic and high expectations for children enhances academic performance. From the findings and conclusion, it is recommended that parents should play a leading role in supporting their children's education since they are the prime educators and the first agents of socialization that expose children to the social and academic world. Parents should set high and realistic expectations for their children's educational attainment. These high and realistic expectations will motivate their children to perform well academically.

Parents should also ensure home supervision by establishing and enforcing the rules and regulations regarding school and home activities as well as providing opportunities and environment conducive for learning. Again, Parent-Teacher

Association should encourage and educate illiterate parents and help parents with disability nominate a person from the immediate family to support their wards.

Teachers should play their role as guardian to help provide the necessary moral, material and psychological support to students from single parents. This assistance will help treat cases of poor academic performance if detected early enough through methods such as focused care, unconditional positive regard, and empathy. This would help restore broken families and help troubled youths become healthy, happy, and productive members of society.

RECOMMENDATIONS

According to the results from the research, these are the recommendations that have been made:

- Most schools may benefit by grouping learners into school families where learners' personal problems can be communicated between the tutors and the parents. The class tutors and school administration should know learner's background.
- The management of primary schools may look for ways to motivate parents to attend school activities. School management should embrace the educational clinics where the parents, tutors and learners come on board and discuss the factors that might be affecting the learners' educational achievements.
- From the fact that the family size has impact on the educational achievement of most learners the parents may be informed on how to plan their family size. Single parents should be educated on the importance of small families that can be easily provided with their requirements.

- The government may educate the public on the importance of education. The results showed that educated people live better than less educated people who have a great advantage of to the national goal.
- Constituency and county bursary offices may help identify the needy learners and more so the single-parent learners and help them to reduce the number of days they spend out of class due to school problems.
- . The community may work together to guide and counsel children on how best to improve academic success. Parents should be sensitized on the importance and good ways of rearing and encouraging their children to attend school. This can be done through media.
- . Teachers and parents as education stakeholder may be very closer to the pupils from single parented families and give them the necessary guidance and counseling in the whole process of maintaining their studies.

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